

Enhancing International Security: A Secure Biometric Data Sharing Framework for Effective Cross-Border Crime and Terrorism Prevention

Georgios Benos
Research & Development
Thridium, Ltd.
London, United Kingdom
gbenos@thridium.com

Konstantinos Koutsoukos
Research & Development
Thridium, Ltd.
London, United Kingdom
konkoutsoukos@thridium.com

Chrysostomos Symvoulidis
Research & Development
Thridium, Ltd.
London, United Kingdom
chris@thridium.com

Dimitrios Drakoulis
Research & Development
Thridium, Ltd.
London, United Kingdom
dimitris@thridium.com

Abstract—Terrorism and international crime prevention is a challenge which requires innovative approaches to law enforcement in order to be effectively addressed. In addition, there is an increasing need to facilitate on the development of higher cooperation among national and international law enforcement agencies towards the better crime control. Yet, due to privacy constraints this is often impossible. For this reason, this paper addresses this critical need by proposing a biometric data sharing framework which is designed to securely exchange such data among law enforcement agencies for such scenarios. The proposed framework, allows a seamless exchange of biometric information, thereby accelerating suspect identification, improving investigative efficacy, and preventing criminal activities. Finally, the framework is evaluated in a real-world scenario to assess its effectiveness, demonstrating its potential to significantly bolster global efforts against terrorism and organized crime.

Index Terms—biometric data exchange, cross-border data exchange, blockchain, terrorism detection, data space.

I. INTRODUCTION

Terrorism and crime represent persistent global challenges, travelling across borders and present serious risks to social security. Law enforcement must adopt new strategies due to the dynamic nature of criminal activity, especially when it comes to exchanging biometric data. The increasing complexity of criminal organizations has led to an urgent need for improved cooperation and information exchange between law enforcement agencies (LEAs) across the globe. In crime investigation, biometric data exchange emerges as a critical tool that provides vital information and proof to effectively counteract international threats. Therefore, the urgent need to combat terrorism and crime on a global scale highlights the necessity of developing strong mechanisms for biometric data exchange.

Building upon this need, the exchange of biometric data has become essential for criminal investigations, particularly when dealing with global criminal activity. Since criminal organizations are increasingly operating across multiple jurisdictions and taking advantage of gaps in international law enforcement coordination, traditional methods of investigation are no longer sufficient. Biometric data, such as fingerprints, facial images

and voice patterns provide a trustworthy and unquestionable way to identify and track individuals across borders and legal systems. Secure sharing of this private information between LEAs accelerates the process of identifying potential suspects, improves the effectiveness of investigations and ultimately prevents further criminal activity.

Moreover, as technology progresses, criminals are becoming more efficient at employing complex strategies to evade detection. In order to overcome these obstacles, biometric evidence is essential because it allows law enforcement to verify identities even in cases in which other forms of identification are compromised. The integration of a secure data sharing platform ensures that sensitive biometric data can be shared seamlessly and legally. That way, security officers can stay up to date with evolving criminal tactics and enhance international cooperation. For this reason, a biometrics data sharing framework is proposed in order to enhance the cross-border collaboration among international LEAs and allow secure sharing of such data.

In more detail, the key contributions of our research are summarized as follows:

- Introduced the architecture of a secure biometric data sharing framework for cross-border exchange towards the early detection of terrorist activities by enabling seamless and secure exchange of biometric information between LEAs, enhancing intelligence capabilities, and facilitating rapid identification of potential threats,
- Evaluated the proposed framework in a real-world scenario in order to assess its effectiveness.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II provides a detailed review of the current state of the art with respect to key issues related to cross-border data exchange, including insuring security in data exchange and tracking the transactions performed in such exchanges to maintain integrity, prevent unauthorized access, and ensure compliance with international regulations and standards. Section III presents the proposed biometric data exchange framework. In Section IV the experiments in order to evaluate the proposed framework

are presented, and a discussion about the extracted outcomes is performed. Finally, Section V summarizes the paper, and discusses further the derived results and suggests future works, based on the current solution.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Cross-border biometric data exchange plays a critical role in the fight against terrorism and crime by providing more accurate, secure, and real-time identification capabilities. It also facilitates better cooperation between nations for that matter. Yet, in order to successfully and securely perform cross-border biometric data exchange, it is important to identify the key technical issues that relate to it. In this research we will mostly focus on two issues. The first issue is related to how can data exchange for personal and biometric data can be performed in a secure manner, while the second is related to the means for ensuring transparent and tamper-proof transaction tracking.

Starting with secure data exchange, this is a heavily researched topic in the literature. There exist contributions in the field of secure data exchange applied in several cases, from healthcare [1]–[3], to data produced by Internet of Things (IoT) devices [4]. All proposed data sharing protocols and schemes in the literature, try to meet specific security needs and natively integrate tools and processes, such as anonymization, and de-identification, in order to secure sensitive data [5]. Furthermore, the authors of [6], suggested that in order to perform secure exchange of (health) data among different institutions that are all part of a given collaborative cloud-based environment, a two-phase security protocol that uses pairing-based cryptography should be used. In addition to the operations performed on the data, specific security and privacy-oriented procedures are equally important. In more detail, the authors of [7] propose a privacy scheme for health data exchange in which, only authorized personnel can access citizens' data that is shared within a cloud platform used for health data sharing. And even though there are relevant studies in the literature that deal with secure data exchange for biometric data [8], there are several issues related to cross-border biometric data exchange that should be addressed, including data sovereignty concerns that arise when biometric data crosses national boundaries [9], or regulatory compliance with differing privacy laws such as the GDPR and local laws in other jurisdictions [10].

Another very important issue has to do with ensuring transparent and tamper-proof transaction tracking. This is a particularly important topic in the field of cross-border biometric data exchange, as it ensures that any exchange of such data is traceable, and can be exploited in order to prevent unauthorized modifications or deletions of records. In most cases in the literature, blockchain technology is utilized in order to address those problems due to its immutability by design [11]. Since each block on the blockchain submitted in the ledger also contains the (cryptographic or not, depending on the scheme) validation of the previously submitted block recursively, the substitution of a single block and its contents demands re-verification of every block submitted after it,

which is very slow, computationally expensive and impractical process. In public blockchains (i.e., blockchains that are in fact decentralized platforms, open to the public), this process is prohibitively expensive to undertake, as even managing to get 50%+1 of the blockchain nodes is a tall task in itself. In private chains (i.e., blockchains restrictive to a given group of organizations) it is considerably easier, as it's practically trivial to get the nodes' consent, but the core problem of having to potentially rewrite tens of thousands of blocks remains. On the other hand, in hybrid blockchain solutions (*a.k.a.*, consortium blockchains), the situation is in-between, as the nodes' consent is easier to secure than on a public chain, but harder than on a private one [12].

The above design principle means that any piece of data stored in a block gets progressively more "crystallized" as new blocks keep appending to the blockchain and by extension, the blockchain is an almost ideal solution for keeping "accounting data", in a practically immutable state, at least when compared to a traditional database. This however warrants extreme care when dealing with any potential data practice guidelines, as is the case with GDPR, since some explicitly state that the data subject can specifically request their data to be deleted (right to be forgotten), which can be extremely challenging as mentioned above [13].

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed platform facilitates secure data exchange among trusted partners, enabling cross-border collaboration in investigations. It allows for the secure storage, sharing, and use of sensitive biometric data (facial images, voiceprints, fingerprints) across multiple LEAs in different European countries.

At its core, the platform provides a robust set of capabilities: trust management, identity verification, data security and sovereignty, as well as standardized interoperability, ensuring that all stakeholders are able to operate within a trusted and secure environment. Each participant in this ecosystem retains complete control over their own data, maintaining sovereignty, while also enabling access to other trusted parties when required. The architecture of the proposed biometric data sharing framework is designed to adhere to stringent legal frameworks governing the use and sharing of biometric data, ensuring compliance with data privacy regulations at both national and international levels.

As also shown in Figure 1, the platform can be either deployed in both cloud and on-premise infrastructures, which are all interconnected. The main components of each federated or cloud deployment are the following: (i) the API component, (ii) the Data Pod, (iii) the Blockchain node, (iv) the Encryption component, (v) the Indexing component, and finally (vi) the Indexed data database. All of these components will be described in detail in the following subsections.

But before describing them, it is important to explain why the cloud deployment is necessary. It is in fact used by LEAs that may not have the required infrastructure to host an on-premise deployment. In such cases, those LEAs can choose to upload their biometric data on the cloud infrastructure.

Fig. 1. Biometric Data Space overview.

A. Solid Protocol - Data Pod

The Solid protocol [14] is a decentralized data storage system that gives data owners complete control over their information, and is the foundation of the proposed data sharing platform. Data pods, which function as isolated servers for storing private biometric information like fingerprints, voice prints, and facial images, are deployed for each LEA independently. Data owners are ensured to maintain control over who has access to their data and under what circumstances by exploiting the capabilities of the Solid protocol. Every LEA officer has access to secure private information storage that satisfies security and privacy requirements. The owner of the data, controls access permissions and can set time-based limitations, usage requirements, and access revocation. The platform uses WebID [15] for identity management, enabling safe user authentication that is essential to preserving the security and transparency of data access.

B. Blockchain Node

Blockchain technology provides an immutable and transparent ledger for recording data transactions, which strengthens the platform's trust and accountability concept. A private blockchain records each request for access to data as well as the responses from the data owner, guaranteeing that all interactions with sensitive data are safely documented. Smart contracts, which automatically manage data access rules based on predefined policies set by the data owner, are further enforced by the blockchain.

For instance, when an organization's officer requests to obtain biometric data, the smart contract checks to see if the requester satisfies the necessary access requirements. If accepted, the transaction is recorded and access privileges are granted in line with the established conditions. This automated procedure preserves legal and regulatory compliance while streamlining international cooperation.

Leveraging blockchain technology however can be quite challenging in this context, mostly due to the ethical and regulatory concerns raised by with data protection rules, such as the European Union's "General Data Protection Regulation"(GDPR). More specifically, GDPR's Article 17, "Right to be forgotten" seems to contradict the usage of any kind of immutable storage, like a blockchain, as it's not possible, or at least highly impractical to delete data from these kinds of storage. The way the data sharing platform tries to deal with this issue is pretty simple, as no personal data is stored in the blockchain. All biometric data are stored in the solid data pods, owned and managed by the relevant agencies, while the blockchain is responsible for storing auxiliary and accounting data, like the initial data request and its response, as well as any access attempt, authorized or otherwise. This data does not contain any personal or identifiable information pertaining to the suspects or officers and is managed at agency-level.

C. API component

The platform makes use of a custom API to enable seamless integration between the Solid data pods and blockchain components as well as to provide the necessary functionality to the

end users through the creation of a number of operations on the pods. By standardizing data retrieval, storage, and access procedures, this API enables LEA officers to engage with the system without requiring extensive technical expertise on the other components. The API provides user registration, session management, and pod initialization features, making it easier for organizations to exploit and manage their data assets. The API also manages access control functions, such as granting and rescinding permissions, guaranteeing that every action is safely recorded on the blockchain. In particular, when a LEA officer makes a request to access biometric data stored on the premises of another organization, the API processes that request by validating it against both the data owner's policies and the blockchain-stored permissions. By performing double validation, the request is bound to comply with the immutable, verified permissions stored on the blockchain as well as the security policies embedded in the Solid pod. In general, the API handles responses to access requests, enabling the requester to retrieve the data in a seamless and controlled manner. As a result, user experience and operational efficiency are improved and the complexity of interacting with the Solid and blockchain systems is significantly reduced.

D. Data Preparation

Prior to storing any type of biometric data in the platform's data pods, specific preliminary actions are performed, in order to ensure data security and facilitate efficient search and retrieval. Each data owner generates metadata for every biometric resource stored, enabling quick and accurate lookup by law enforcement officers. This indexing process, which involves creating hashed values and metadata for each biometric record, allows for fast identification of potential matches without directly sharing the raw data. During the execution of a search query, only the hashed values and associated metadata are exchanged, ensuring that sensitive information is not exposed. In case a match is found, the requester can view the indexed data and, if necessary, submit a formal request to access the original encrypted data stored in the data pod.

In terms of security, the platform ensures that all data stored in the data pods is encrypted by the owner organization before being stored, with encryption keys managed as part of the data owner's access control policies. This method safeguards the data confidentiality and permits restricted access only upon authorization.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The main functional testing of the Data Space component, including the scenarios "Data Offering" and "Data Exchange", took place in a temporary deployment of the software platform in a proprietary infrastructure, in coordination and with support from the TENSOR consortium partners. For the aforementioned scenarios, we provide the sequence of the steps executed to evaluate the components and corresponding screenshots of the execution environment.

A. Initial Setup

To ensure the robustness and functionality of our Distributed and Privacy-Preserving Biometrics Management and Sharing Framework, extensive and comprehensive functional testing was conducted. Our service was deployed on an isolated test Virtual Machine (VM) where the Solid, blockchain, and API components were properly set up and tested as part of the testing procedure.

Users only need an internet connection to access the deployed URL and set up MetaMask [16], a digital wallet, on their browser to interact with the blockchain components of the system. Metamask in itself is not necessary, as any smart wallet can interact with the blockchain, yet it was used mainly because its ease of use, as expected users of the final product would not have an extremely high technological expertise level, along with its popularity in cryptocurrency exchanges.

In our capacity as administrators, we used the aforementioned Solid Data Pods inside the framework to represent various LEAs and mimic real-world scenarios. Every Pod was assigned to a distinct user, emulating the functional arrangement of several LEAs on the platform. For the testing purposes we created two testing Pods. This configuration was essential for verifying the proposed framework's inter-agency data sharing capabilities. We then started the functional testing by simulating the data requests and exchanges that occur between these Pods. The way that biometric data is typically shared between different LEAs was replicated by this process.

B. User Preparation

During the initialization of the Data Sharing platform, a single user account and its associated data pod are created automatically, based on preconfigured secrets. This account acts as an administrator for that particular deployment of the Data Sharing Platform and along with being a fully-fledged user, it retains the special permission to create new user accounts and pods by triggering the "POST@/api/user/register" endpoint. In addition, this account is linked to a "faucet" address in the blockchain, that is responsible for transferring a set amount of tokens to newly registered accounts, as well as posting blockchain operations as a "system" entity, when a specific user is not involved in a specific process.

For the testing scenarios, the built-in "administrator" account, created two new user accounts / data pods, acting as a "Data Provider" and "Data Consumer" respectively. Since, the Administrator account is able to create the new data pods, but do not have any in-built access rights in the new pods after they are created, it is necessary for the new users to perform the initialization on their own data pods right after their initial login (as also depicted in Figure 2). This process is facilitated by calling the "GET@/api/users/initialize" endpoint available by the API component, which performs all the the necessary initialization operations automatically. These include the creation of an index file, which keeps a list of key/value objects, associating the uploaded resources with their hashed and indexed value, as defined by the Indexing Mechanism, essentially allowing the retrieval of resources by

Fig. 2. Login to Solid Server.

both their URL and hash, as well as the creation of a new blockchain account, and its association with the newly created data pod, and finally the initialization of the "Distributed Data Catalogue", storing the actual hashed values of the resources, used by the indexing mechanism.

Finally, the user received the generated private/public key pair used for signing the blockchain transactions in later scenario steps, which can be imported to the user's smart wallet of choice. It is worth noting that the Data Space does not retain, store or handle these private keys in any way and it is the sole responsibility of the pod owner to properly and securely store them.

C. Data Preparation

While it is perfectly viable to use the Data Sharing platform by itself, it can also be used as a core component in a bigger data management flow, along with other components or services. In this specific setup, after the initialization of each data pod, the data indexing mechanism was responsible for populating the Distributed Biometric Catalogue in every data pod. The Catalogue was hosted in a special sub-directory where the indexer service had full access rights and was treated as a co-owner, and could use this Catalogue to match vectorized biometric hashes (photos, voice clips and fingerprints) against it.

In addition to the indexing mechanism, a new, custom cryptographic component plays a big part in fostering a secure and safe environment around the data sharing process. Even though the integrated Solid WebID-TLS protocol [17] is perfectly adequate for personal usage and social data, as was intended by the platform's original developers, in the landscape of extremely sensitive biometric data and LEAs, extra layers of security are needed. In addition to the standard TLS encryption, the indexed data used for processing were also encrypted homomorphically, allowing for mathematical processing without the need for decryption by the comparator module, while the raw biometrics were also encrypted using standard symmetric encryption, with the shared key

itself stored and encrypted asymmetrically in the blockchain component of the data sharing platform.

The indexing and encryption components were coordinated with the Data Sharing Platform as parts of a larger Data Space, while special data space connectors were used to handle the encoding, decoding, key management and general access policies, according to European and International Data Space standards [18].

D. Data Request

After verifying and logging into the system, the owners could add resources to the Data Pods. They provided the direct path they wished to store the resource (in this case an image), the file to be uploaded and optionally a filename and content type. If a filename was specified, the uploaded resource would be renamed as the new `fileName` immediately. In case the original file name was also restricted in the context of inter-agency data sharing agreements, and the content-type was used only in edge cases where either the data was in some proprietary, unrecognizable format, such as intermediate data generated by forensic tools, or the data itself needed to be interpreted in a different manner than originally (*e.g.*, parsing dataset files like JSON, as simple text).

The index of the uploaded resource was generated and associated with the raw resource via the assistance of the indexing mechanism. After the data had been made available in the data provider's Solid pod, the other user (data requestor) made a request to gain access to this specific resource. This step involved, making the actual request through the API and also writing it to the blockchain as a transaction. The request contained: the recipients WebID, the requested resource's index (acquired from indexing mechanism), the requested access type, and the requestor's preconfigured asymmetric (public) key.

The API response contained the raw hexadecimal data that needed to be submitted in the smart contract for the transaction to be written and stored. As depicted in Figure 3, the requestor then used Metamask (or any other smart wallet of their choice, as mentioned above) to submit the transaction data in the blockchain, using a minuscule amount of the tokens that were transferred from the faucet at the initialization step. The above process ensured absolute accountability and non-repudiation, as making additional data requests fully automatically, without the requestor's express consent and participation, would compromise the absolute trust needed between users and the system for the accounting and arbitration of the data-exchange process.

E. Data Response & Access

When the transaction was confirmed, the data owner could either retrieve the request manually using the relevant endpoint `"GET@/api/requests"` or check their notifications using `"GET@/api/notifications"` which would provide the request id to retrieve. In the response, the user could view the WebID where the request came from, the requested index, the

Fig. 3. Smart Contract Submission.

access type (read, write, or full) that was asked and the date it was submitted.

Later, the data provider had to generate a response to this request. The response contained: the request ID, the recipient blockchain address, the resource URL, the duration of the given access, the response type, the asymmetric encryption key, and optionally a free-text message. In similar manner, upon the successful creation of the response, the transaction was generated and had to be signed and deployed to the smart contract with MetaMask.

Finally, the data owner modified the access rights, giving as parameters (i) the path of the resource and (ii) the webId of the requesting user. After the response object was posted on the blockchain, the data requestor was able to perform similar steps to either retrieve the response manually via "GET@/api/responses/", or check their notifications. To conclude the test flow, and given that the response was positive and the access policy has been modified, the data requestor could retrieve the resource, either by using the index and the corresponding Pod, by triggering the appropriate "GET@/api/resources/{pod-name}/{index}" or by using the full URL found in the response object, by triggering "GET@/api/{pod-name}/{path/to/file}". In that case, they retrieved, as shown in Figure 4, and could use the image until the access rights were revoked, or the initial time frame, specified in the data response expires.

Lastly, to verify the proper functionality of the component, the access rights of this particular image, were modified manually by the data owner, and on subsequent access attempts, the data requestor gets a message clarifying that the requested resource can't be retrieved. For the testing process we used Swagger to trigger the implemented endpoints. At this moment it may seem somehow complex to trigger all these different endpoints to perform a data access request. As the project

Fig. 4. Response of resource request.

evolves, and more components are integrated together, this process will be smoother since a lot of these functionalities will be triggered automatically by the different services or the unified dashboard component.

F. Data & User Accounting

In parallel to the main data flow, each time a CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operation was made on any resource, like the data requestor accessing the file, a data access request was generated and stored on the blockchain, containing the WebId of the logged in user (if available), the timestamp of the access attempt, the result (whether it was successful or denied), and the type (read, write, update, delete, control). By cross-referencing the data access objects with the data requests and responses, the LEAs got a powerful tool to help them monitor their data and audit their policies.

In this regard, any data access request that is successful must take place in a time frame specified in the data response and be of an approved type, while every other successful data access (except those by services with special permissions, like the indexer) should raise an alarm. A special case of alarm is when a data access is denied, while still under a data access response, meaning the data provider has revoked access manually and prematurely, and by extension the data requestor is entitled to further explanations.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a secure cross-border biometric data exchange framework towards the effective prevention of crime and prevention. The proposed framework can be used by LEAs in order to collaborate and exchange biometric data in a secure, distributed manner. Each LEA has complete control over their stored data on their pod and along with permission access rights on it. The framework is accompanied by blockchain technology in order to provide a transparent and immutable way for recording data transactions towards a higher trust of the platform. All interconnections between the cloud infrastructure and the on-premise deployments of the enrolled LEAs are managed by the API component in order to streamline the integration process. The proposed framework was put under evaluation in order to assess its components and the overall effectiveness. In more detail:

- The registration of new users and data pods is functional in its combination of Solid and blockchain operations, but lacks many QoL (Quality of Life) features of a commercial product (e.g., integration with SSO - Single Sign On services).
- The initialization phase customises the contents of the newly created data pod and delivers the blockchain private key directly to the pod owner, to prevent the undermining of non-repudiation in blockchain operations. It is a compromise, between Solid's principle of absolute pod ownership and user convenience or integration with external services.
- The data accounting operations recorded on the blockchain, present an ad-hoc way to secure both the data owner, against unauthorised access attempts and the data provider, against unauthorised permission revocations, while having a relative minimal impact on the user experience, during the data exchange operation.
- The automatic generation of data requests and responses by the API, take away the bulk of the cognitive load of having to deal with blockchain operations from the end users, while still needing a degree of manual user interaction, in order to ensure non-repudiation of the request/response.
- The data exchange itself, takes place in a secure environment, assured both by Solid's security-by-design principles and bespoke encryption modules, with minimal (but not negligible) impact in exchange speed.

Overall, the experiments showed relatively promising results, as either a standalone platform to promote cooperation and transparency in future LEA cooperation, or as an integrated part of a bigger forensic data analysis platform. The request/response data flow, limited the needs of prior communication between the partners and presented a transparent way to safeguard both parties in terms of their respective obligations, without agreeing to potentially arbitrary or limiting rules of a more centralised system.

As far as our next steps are concerned, the largest priority is the overhauling of the internal Solid IDP module used for pod and user management, in order to make it more compatible with industry standards. This will also make the process of deploying and setting up a copy of the Biometric Data Sharing Platform more straightforward and accessible for less technologically savvy.

Another future step includes the enrichment of the blockchain smart contract with more information that could potentially assist the LEAs make more informed decisions in whether they want to grant access or not (e.g., matching scores generated by the comparator analysis, or any pre-agreed binding agreements in government level). After those improvements, a new round of testing will take place. In more detail the framework will be put under evaluation in a real-world scenario with the participation of LEA partners from the TENSOR project, which will provide feedback that will shape the platform in the further future while it will also test the platform's scalability in terms of higher load scenarios or

data latency issues, among others.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has received funding from the EU Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under GA No 101073920 (TENSOR project).

REFERENCES

- [1] K. Koutsoukos, C. Symvoulidis, A. Kiourtis, A. Mavrogiorgou, S. Dimopoulou, and D. Kyriazis, "Emergency health protocols supporting health data exchange, cloud storage, and indexing," in *HEALTHINF*, 2022, pp. 597–604.
- [2] C. Symvoulidis, A. Mavrogiorgou, A. Kiourtis, G. Marinos, and D. Kyriazis, "Facilitating health information exchange in medical emergencies," in *2021 International Conference on e-Health and Bioengineering (EHB)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–4.
- [3] A. Kiourtis, A. Graziani, A. Mavrogiorgou, C. Symvoulidis, K. Mavrogiorgos, and D. Kyriazis, "A health information exchange protocol supporting bluetooth-based messages," in *2021 International Conference on Information Systems and Advanced Technologies (ICISAT)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–6.
- [4] Y. Zhang, L. Bo, and Q. Ma, "A secure data exchange protocol for the internet of things," in *Contemporary Research on E-business Technology and Strategy: International Conference, iCETS 2012, Tianjin, China, August 29-31, 2012, Revised Selected Papers*. Springer, 2012, pp. 224–231.
- [5] T. Ecarot, B. Fraikin, F. Ouellet, L. Lavoie, M. McGilchrist, and J.-F. Ethier, "Sensitive data exchange protocol suite for healthcare," in *2020 IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–7.
- [6] M. Masud and M. S. Hossain, "Secure data-exchange protocol in a cloud-based collaborative health care environment," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 77, pp. 11 121–11 135, 2018.
- [7] C.-L. Chen, T.-T. Yang, and T.-F. Shih, "A secure medical data exchange protocol based on cloud environment," *Journal of medical systems*, vol. 38, pp. 1–12, 2014.
- [8] K. Kyriakou, A. Apostolaras, P. Velentzas, I. Syrigos, S. Maglavera, S. Evangelatos, E. Veroni, and T. Korakis, "Biometrics data space: Ensuring trustworthy and secure data exchange for suspect identification," in *2024 5th International Conference in Electronic Engineering, Information Technology & Education (EEITE)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–6.
- [9] N. Da Silva Carvalho, J. Jabbarpour, L. Temple, I. M. Belacort, U. I. Barturen, M. Kortlander, V. Sanchez Pelaez, E. Areizaga Sanchez, and F. Mureddu, "A more inclusive europe through personal data sovereignty in cross-border digital public services," in *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Electronic Governance*, 2023, pp. 63–71.
- [10] M. Nalin, I. Baroni, G. Faiella, M. Romano, F. Matrisciano, E. Gelenbe, D. M. Martinez, J. Dumortier, P. Natsiavas, K. Votis *et al.*, "The european cross-border health data exchange roadmap: Case study in the italian setting," *Journal of biomedical informatics*, vol. 94, p. 103183, 2019.
- [11] E. Landerreche and M. Stevens, "On immutability of blockchains," in *Proceedings of 1st ERCIM Blockchain Workshop 2018*. European Society for Socially Embedded Technologies (EUSSET), 2018.
- [12] A. K. Sharma, D. M. Sharma, N. Purohit, S. A. Sharma, and A. Khan, "Blockchain technology: Myths, realities and future," in *Blockchain Technology*. CRC Press, 2022, pp. 163–180.
- [13] E. Politou, F. Casino, E. Alepis, and C. Patsakis, "Blockchain mutability: Challenges and proposed solutions," *IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computing*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 1972–1986, 2021.
- [14] S. Project, "Solid project," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://solidproject.org/>
- [15] WebID, "Webid," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://webid-solutions.com/>
- [16] Metamask, "Metamask," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://metamask.io/>
- [17] B. H. Toby Inkster, Henry Story, "Webid-tls webid authentication over tls," 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://w3c.github.io/WebID/spec/tls/>
- [18] IDSA, "International data spaces," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://internationaldataspaces.org/>